

RESEARCH ARTICLE

2023, vol. 10, issue 2, 28 – 38

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15254222>

FROM NOVICE TO FLUENT: UNRAVELING THE ROLE OF SCAFFOLDING IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING

BELAID LOUIZA

Department of English, Ibn Khaldoun University, Tiaret, ALGERIA, louiza.belaid@univ-tiaret.dz<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9802-4195>

Abstract

In this paper, we aim to investigate the incorporation of scaffolding strategies in the classroom, with a specific focus on stimulating and reinforcing the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD). The main objective is to unveil the challenges that pupils face when learning a foreign language and to investigate the function of psycholinguistic techniques in improving the social and communication skills of young learners, enabling them to be self-regulated and autonomous. To collect data, a mixed-method design is employed, using both a questionnaire and a participant observation. The questionnaire evaluates the extent to which elementary school teachers of English in Tissemsilt, Algeria, use scaffolding in their classrooms. The participant observation aims to provide valuable insights into the functional use of these strategies in teaching English, specifically focusing on their impact on 3rd grade learners. The findings reveal that while the teachers exhibit their awareness of the scaffolding practical framework and its potential implications, the functional application of these strategies did not effectively target the learners' zone of proximal development. In this prospect, It is advisable to include psycholinguistic approaches in the training programs for teachers. This will promote their awareness of the scope and modernize the teaching strategies in foreign language learning.

Keywords: *Scaffolding framework; zone of proximal development; teaching strategies; training program.*

1. INTRODUCTION and BACKGROUND

In the field of education, disparities often arise in terms of performance, participation, or inclusivity. The task of searching for solutions in a specific field can be overwhelming and stagnant, thus, the initiative to solve educational gaps through the application of other approaches in different fields may reach promising avenues. To reach this end, one area of interest in the field of psycholinguistics is the application of scaffolding. intended to provide support to learners to facilitate their learning process. Scaffolding gradually shifts the learning responsibility from teachers to learners through instructional strategies and resources. This study aims to unleash the challenges pupils face in learning foreign languages and to implement functional approaches in the classroom. By examining the theories related to the scaffolds and zone of proximal development, this study sheds light on psychological and neural aspects, while highlighting the importance of psycholinguistic methods in language learning. Scaffolding can be applied in contexts of language learning and acquisition, where tutors simplify language, emphasize basic words, and provide contextual cues to assist learners in understanding and generating language. Although scaffolding originates from the field of education, it is consistent with the principles explored in psycholinguistics; the study of cognitive processes and mechanisms involved in language development. Consequently, integrating scaffolding strategies into psycholinguistic research will positively shift the learning outcomes.

2. PSYCHOLINGUISTIC FIELDWORK

Scientific research on the human brain places a great deal of emphasis on psychological aspects of language, which has led to the fusion between psychology and linguistics in the study of language. Language and the human brain form an interesting field of study that explores the complex connections between cognition and communication. Psycholinguistics, the interdisciplinary domain that emerges from this exploration, focuses on understanding how the brain processes, acquires, and comprehends language. Researchers in this field combine principles from psychology and linguistics, providing valuable insights into the mind's perception of language. By merging scaffolding strategies into psycholinguistic research, educators can unlock the potential for positive learning outcomes and create inclusive learning environments. The scaffolding techniques provide valuable support to learners, enabling them to build upon their existing skills and knowledge, fostering greater independence and self-confidence. According to Purba, (2018) *“psycholinguistics can be defined as the study of mind and language. It is concerned with the relationship between the human mind and the language as it examines the processes that occur in brain while producing and perceiving language”* (p. 47) The study of how language and speech are mentally processed is known as psycholinguistics, and the representation and processing of language in the brain is its core area of interest. In a similar vein, psycholinguistics deals with the devices of the human brain that processes and represents language in the brain; it attempts to understand what enables humans to acquire and use language correctly and how the concept of psycholinguistics is related to the study of how humans can appropriately manage language (Field, 2004; Traxler & Gernsbacher, 2006; Traxler, 2012; Heidari, 2022).

2.1 THE COGNITIVIST PARADIGM

Cognitive theory is a theoretical framework that seeks to understand how the mind operates with a focus on cognitive functions like perception, attention, memory, and problem-solving. Cognitive psychologists frequently employ a range of scientific methods, including experiments, observations, and cognitive assessments, to delve into the intricacies of mental processes. Their main objective is to unveil the fundamental mechanisms and structures that govern cognitive functions. To achieve this, they often rely on models and theories, which enable them to elucidate and forecast human behavior based on principles of information processing. According to Sternberg, (2008) *“cognitivism is the view that mental processes can be understood as information processing, and that the mind can be studied using scientific methods.”* (p. 4). Cognitivism asserts that humans are not just imitative and productive of what they hear and perceive, but they are also creative by nature. It emphasizes the receiving, organization, and storage of information within the human mind as a learning theory, connecting it to the operation of a computer as an information processor. Cognitivism is a term that encompasses a range of objectives aimed at understanding the complex processes through which the mind assimilates information. It also seeks to explore the underlying principles behind human creativity and problem-solving. This theory sheds light on how individuals process knowledge and shape their perception of the world by acknowledging the cognitive abilities of the mind. As a result, it offers valuable insights into effective educational techniques and learning strategies. Therefore, the principles of this theory can be outlined as follows:

- a) Internal Mental Processes
- b) Active Learner Involvement
- c) Study of Mental Processes
- d) Language Construction
- e) Dynamic Personalized Understanding

Cognitive development refers to the process by which our thinking develops through different stages. Cognitive development is not a random process but involves deliberate efforts and mental processes that enable us to analyze and evaluate the world around us. Additionally, our understanding and interpretation of the environment are shaped through experimentation and construction. Hence, language learning, in particular, plays a crucial role in cognitive development. Piaget, as cited in Johnson (2014), has maintained that humans go through four stages of cognitive development:

- 1) First Stage: During infancy where babies rely on their fundamental five senses to comprehend the world surrounding them.
- 2) Second Stage: Between the ages of 2 and 7, in which children engage in symbolic thinking, using toys and imagination.
- 3) Third Stage: From ages 7 to 12, children undergo the development of logical thinking and concrete reasoning, which is applicable to concepts of time, space, and quantity.

4) Fourth Stage: The formal operational stage commences at the age of 12 where abstract reasoning and hypothetical thinking become prominent.

2.1.1 LANGUAGE PERCEPTION

Language perception is the process of creating and understanding words, phrases, and sentences from written or spoken information. It involves a continuous interaction between bottom-up processing, driven by the analysis of incoming stimulus features, and top-down processing, fueled by higher-level expectations and activation of knowledge. This dynamic nature of language processing highlights its multifaceted nature, which encompasses different levels of representation, in addition to the retrieval of lexical and conceptual information from memory (Levelt, 2001). Linguistic processing, on the other hand, exhibits remarkable flexibility and context dependency, with lexical and syntactic processing occurring simultaneously and interactively. This sheds light on the fluidity and adaptability inherent in language processing, while also emphasizing the significance of vocabulary and grammar as integral components of language (Heidari, 2022). The individuals' perception of language varies from one learner to another, depending on their skills, type of intelligence, level of motivation and personal interest (Treiman et al, 2003)

2.1.2 LANGUAGE COMPREHENSION

Language comprehension is a natural and unconscious process that occurs in humans. Children are immersed in a varied range of spoken languages from birth, establishing the framework for their ability to comprehend and develop connections with written language. Every linguistic information young kids hear, whether spoken, sung, or read to them, accumulates in their schemata, acting as a useful resource as they grow and develop. In this context, "comprehension" refers to an individual's ability to grasp and make sense of information, which includes their ability to understand both spoken and written language. It evaluates language processing and comprehension, influencing education and communication.

Wernicke (1974) has asserted that *"the lesion of the left posterior superior temporal gyrus produces a complex disturbance of speech, which consists in a defect of comprehension, whilst the power of utterance remains intact"* (p. 17). The way people understand and even interpret the written, spoken, gestured or signed versions of a specific language is called language comprehension. The intricate process of linking the Wernicke's area to the Broca's area is solely carried out by the human brain. This neural mechanism plays a crucial role in transmitting messages and comprehending them. It is noteworthy to mention that the Wernicke's area is part of the brain located within the left hemisphere, it is primarily responsible for language comprehension, and thus any damage in this area might result in longitudinal difficulties of comprehension and response.

Individuals must be able to decode words to understand what is being read. Language comprehension, in this regard, is a complex process involving many cognitive processes that work together to interpret the meaning of a spoken or written message. Linguists discuss in "The Scientific Guide to Reading" how humans decipher words to give meaning to what we read and hear. (Bertram, 2013), hence, this aforementioned requires language comprehension skills. In the field of psycholinguistics, language comprehension refers to an individual's ability to understand and make sense of information conveyed verbally. It specifically evaluates a person's capacity to understand spoken words, irrespective of whether they can accomplish this skill proficiently or not. Within linguistics, human speech functions are broadly classified into two primary categories:

- ✚ First, understanding language when speaking/writing, or understanding language when listening/reading, is called comprehension, and the ability to produce language, either orally or in writing, is called production.
- ✚ Second, since psycholinguistics studies the relationship between the human mind and language, knowledge of the factors that enhance or impair language comprehension in mentally and neurologically stable/unstable individuals is an integral part of research.

2.1.3 LANGUAGE PRODUCTION

Language production is a cognitive process which aims at creating a linguistic message to convey a desired meaning to the listener, this process involves activating mental representations of words, grammatical structures and knowledge of speech, organizing them into a coherent and appropriate message, and transforming them into motor commands to produce speech. Language production requires the simultaneous processing of multiple demands on cognitive resources; speakers must balance the need to produce language quickly and fluently with the need to produce accurate and grammatical language (Levelt, 2001). In the context of English language teaching, scaffolding is essential for facilitating language development for pupils in primary schools. It helps with several language development processes, including vocabulary expansion, understanding of grammar, speaking

practice, and writing support. To direct discussions, facilitate the clarification of ideas, and enhance reading comprehension, instructors may use scaffolding strategies. As an illustration, role-playing and drama exercises strengthen oral communication skill sets, while feedback and error correction give either positive or negative responses. Therefore, elementary school pupils can ultimately develop confidence, proficiency, and autonomy in using the English language through encompassing scaffolding in language instruction; setting an adequate framework for their academic and personal involvement.

As far as language production is concerned, pupils with disorders are impaired and may encounter challenges in expressing themselves verbally. To be precise, language disorders occur when an individual has difficulties in understanding, sharing thoughts, feelings, and ideas and using language in functional ways. As per Beitchman & Brownlie (2014) *“developmental language impairment / developmental language disorder are used in some contexts to refer to language impairment emerging in childhood, distinguished from acquired language impairment”* (p. 02); Individuals with Social Communication Disorders experience challenges in various aspects of social interactions, including verbal and nonverbal communication. Individuals with autism spectrum disorder as well as those who experienced traumatic brain injuries face challenges in social communication. (The American Speech Language Hearing Association, 2010). In this prospect, pupils who suffer from this type of language disorder encounter difficulties in perceiving, comprehending, and producing language. Consequently, their integration with learners with no disability might pose challenges for teachers.

3. ZONE OF PROXIMAL DEVELOPMENT

The zone of proximal development (ZPD) is a concept in psycholinguistics, it was introduced by the psychologist Vygotsky (1933). It refers to the difference between what a learner can do without assistance and what they can do with assistance which is typically achieved through “scaffolding” (Sazali et al., 2022). Vygotsky has asserted that learning occurs when a more knowledgeable individual, such as a teacher or trainer, guides learners through the learning process.

The zone of proximal development is the distance between the actual development level as determined by independent problem solving and the level of potential development as determined through problem solving under adult guidance or in collaboration with more capable peers (Vygotsky, 1978, p. 86).

The Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) is a fundamental concept in education that refers to a number of abilities that a learner can perform with the guidance and support of an educator or a more competent peer. It serves as a transitional phase where learners can make remarkable improvement with the support of a skilled tutor. According to Vygotsky, the ZPD varies among individuals, depending on their inherent competencies and skills. Therefore, it is within this zone that effective learning occurs (Cornell, 2023). Further, the zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) plays a crucial role in the process of language acquisition. This zone provides learners with the opportunity to receive significant feedback on their language usage and enhance their vocabulary and knowledge of grammatical structures. To proceed, different activities, such as guided conversations, role-playing, group work, and collaborative projects, can be used. By engaging in guided conversations, learners can actively practice their language skills while receiving expert guidance and correction. This interactive approach allows them to refine their language abilities and gain confidence in their communication. Experimenting with different language scenarios in role-playing exercises can help learners practically develop their linguistic competence in a safe and controlled environment. Group work and collaborative projects further promote language learning within the ZPD. Through group works, learners can exchange ideas, share knowledge, and collectively solve problems. This collaborative approach fosters a stimulating environment, motivating learners to actively participate and contribute to the learning process.

4. SCAFFOLDING IN EDUCATION

Scaffolding is an approach in which a teacher provides support and guidance to learners to help them reach a higher average and a good level of understanding, one of the prominent linguists who insisted on its relevance is Vygotsky (1978), the aforementioned thoughts have displayed the importance of scaffolding in promoting the learners' skills development; Vygotsky believed that through continuous assistance, learners could progress professionally. The scaffolding technique enables the pupils to build new skills and knowledge in a supportive environment; it represents the support given to enable them to perform tasks in their way, as maintained by Vygotsky (1978) *“scaffolding is a necessary process where the teacher gradually transfers the responsibility for learning to the learner, allowing them to become independent thinkers.”*(p. 86), Thus, scaffolding is prerequisite

in promoting independence and critical thinking in learners, as the teacher gradually releases control and allows the learner to lead and self-regulate their learning.

Rogoff (1990) in her book 'Apprenticeship in Thinking' has asserted that *"scaffolding is not just about teaching a concept, but also about encouraging higher-order thinking skills and metacognition."* (p. 56) Targeting Bloom's taxonomy and higher-order thinking is one of the aims of applying scaffolding and this would inevitably increase critical thinking and self-reflection. In this prospect, the teachers' responsibility extends beyond merely providing information to students; it includes optimizing and facilitating their learning process, as well as leading them through multiple assignments and experiences. As argued by Gonulal (2018) *"scaffolding is not simply synonymous with teacher support. Scaffolding is specific just-in-time support that gives students the pedagogical push that enables them to work at a higher level of activity."* (p. 03)

4.1 SCAFFOLDING DEVELOPMENTAL ASSISTANCE

Scaffolding can be incorporated in various ways when working with foreign language learners. Some essential instructional techniques for scaffolding include modeling, bridging, contextualizing, schema building, re-presenting text, and developing metacognition. First, in the modeling technique, learners are given concrete examples of what is expected from them, providing clear guidelines for their tasks and activities. Besides tasks, teachers can demonstrate proper language patterns and vocabulary that learners might need while completing their assignments. Second, through bridging techniques, teachers trigger the learners' prior knowledge to build their competencies. This method could help in establishing a personal connection between the learners' lives and the subject and navigate the academic language they encounter in class. (Gonulal & Loewen, 2018; Hussein, 2022)

Third, the contextualizing technique can be achieved through the use of verbal and nonverbal aids (realia) like pictures, videos, and analogies. Schema building is another technique where teachers assist learners in connecting new information to their existing knowledge structures (n+1); the outcome is their ability to have a constructive output. For example, before a reading task, students may preview the text's title, illustrations, and charts to activate their background knowledge and effectively incorporate new information. Re-presenting texts involves changing the genre or the type of a text into another distinct form. Finally, the learners' self-regulation and autonomy can be achieved through developing metacognition whereby the learners' metacognition is nurtured through modeling strategies such as think-aloud and self-assessment activities. The successful application of these strategies promotes a higher level of competence as it demands considerable skill and preparation from teachers to assist learners with the help they need. (Reiser, 2004; Ameri & Seyyedrezaei, 2016; Gonulal & Loewen, 2018; Abdelshaheed, 2019).

5. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The data tools used in this study include a questionnaire, which was administered to twenty teachers, newly recruited, in different primary schools, who are in charge of teaching English to third graders after the planning of the new Algerian Reform by the Ministry of Education. In addition to classroom observations in five primary schools, where the sample depicted their new teaching journey in these primary schools. Thus, we attempted to search for the possible use of modern approaches of teaching and how they scaffold in English classes. By combining quantitative and qualitative data, the study aims to disclose the pupils' performance in English, their communication skills development, as well as the new experiences of teachers and the challenges they are facing with elementary school learners.

5.1 SAMPLING

Twenty teachers of English from third-grade primary schools in Tissemsilt -Algeria- were selected to participate in this study (N=20), out of a total population of 25 teachers. Our sample was selected via a non-probabilistic sampling method. 10% of the participating teachers have no teaching experience though they hold either a bachelor's degree in English (Licence), Master's degree or a diploma in Translation and Interpretation. Due to the recent reform of English language teaching in the Algerian primary schools, each assigned teacher was in charge of teaching third-grade pupils. Despite the relatively small number of participants, we firmly believe that their responses will yield invaluable insights for future educational planning and curriculum development in Algeria. We acknowledge the necessity for additional research and a larger sample size to comprehend the impact of English language planning in Algerian primary schools and to effectively generalize the outcomes of this endeavor.

5.2 TEACHERS' QUESTIONNAIRE ANALYSIS

Our purpose from the survey is to gather demographic information and educational background data. The gender distribution of our sample is composed as follows, 60% of participants are female teachers whereas 40% are male teachers, this prevails that the majority of teachers who responded to the questionnaire are females, noting that the majority of recruited teachers are females corresponding to the gender gap that is increasing worldwide regarding the high number of females in all fields including education (Belaid, 2020). Our sample academic qualification varies, 75% has a master degree; 15% has a license degree, while 10% of the sample has a doctorate degree, making it the least common highest academic qualification among the group. We can state that this data help us in understanding the level of education and expertise among the teachers. Thus, it would facilitate for the researchers to detect whether they know how to scaffold or not.

Question 01: Do you work as a teacher on a full-time basis?

It is a prerequisite to be acquainted with the respondents' current work situation. This information discloses that there could be a diverse workforce within the teaching profession, with some individuals being employed full-time while others rely on part-time employment. The difference between full-time and part-time teaching can have an impact on pupils' achievement. The aim behind this question is to understand whether our selected sample oversees other sessions in another schools or not; concentrating on one context only will enable the teacher to be more focused and systematic. Additionally, the question holds significant importance in assessing the workload and commitment of the teachers. As clarified in the figure below, 75% of the sample have answered positively to our question, which means that they are currently working in another primary school to meet the required time allotment specified in the school timetable, while 25% of them answered with "no" claiming that they are working in one school only. It is important to acknowledge that the participants who are pursuing their doctoral degrees also dedicate additional hours to teaching at university. Hence, they are already engaged in part-time jobs, which may limit their concentration on their teaching task.

Figure 1. Teaching English at different primary schools

Question 02: Was any of the subject categories listed below included in your educational training program?

Upon English planning in primary school, many teachers –specialized in English- were recruited in different primary schools to teach English as a second foreign language after French. Calling upon inspectors specialized in the English language is essential to enhance the professional development of teachers. The purpose behind the above query is to gather information about the rubrics and sections that are covered in their training besides their knowledge and expertise in the field. From the responses, we can denote that the majority of teachers have been trained in foundational areas such as "Mastery of the Educational Syllabus" and "Modes of Assessment." Nevertheless, there are some delinquencies where fewer teachers have mentioned, such as "ICT skills for teaching," "scaffolding Techniques," "teaching learners with special needs," and "teaching in a multicultural or multilingual setting." The defaults found in these trainings will create another gap in teaching especially in a context where the mother tongue and the target language share separate linguistic systems, i.e. Algerian dialectal Arabic and English.

Table 1. Key Themes in National Training Programs

Themes	Percentage %	
	Yes	No
Mastery of the Educational Syllabus	70%	30%
Modes of Assessment	95%	05%
Integrating ICT in Teaching	60%	40%
Classroom Conduct and Management	75%	25%
Addressing Gender Perspectives	20%	80%
Scaffolding Techniques	30%	70%
Multilingual Classroom Strategies	35%	65%
Cross-Curricular Skills	55%	45%

Question 03: What challenges/impairments do your pupils encounter?

It is important to note that pupils come to school with several needs; they could be psychological, physical or social. Thus, the question aims to uncover the pupils' challenging impairments at school. As shown in the table below, 85% of teachers report that the majority of pupils frequently face challenges in maintaining attention. While 65% of teachers argue that pupils are often hyperactive, by which their hyperactivity is not easily controlled. In addition, comprehension and communication problems were mentioned by some teachers with a percentage of 55% while production problems received a higher percentage (80%). Other situations such as dysgraphia, cluttering and stuttering problems are raised with lower percentages (35%, 5%). Fear of public speaking affects 20% of students, as displayed in the table below. There is a considerable rate for anxiety too with a percentage of 50%. The findings show that if pupils' difficulties are not addressed appropriately, they may become permanent and negatively impact their academic performance. From the teachers' responses, we notice that many approaches can be used to deal with these psychological difficulties. Some suggested techniques include creating a safe learning environment, providing scaffolding and support for pupils, treating pupils equally, and giving individual attention and support according to the needs of each individual.

Table 2. Pupils' type of difficulty

Situations	Choice	
	Yes	No
Comprehension Problems	55%	45%
Communication Problems	55%	45%
Production Problems	80%	20%
Stuttering/Cluttering	35%	65%
Dysgraphia	05%	95%
Auditory Processing disorders	65%	35%
Hyperactivity	65%	35%
Attention Deficiency	85%	15%
High Levels of Anxiety	50%	50%
Fear of Public Exposure	20%	80%

Question 4: How would you approach scaffolding in the classroom to work on the pupils' zone of proximal development?

The purpose of raising this question is to collect information from the selected participants on their understanding of scaffolding strategies to support their pupils' academic development. The responses to this question help to identify the weaknesses where additional support or professional development may be needed to promote reflective teaching and improve the learning outcomes. Based on the responses provided, we have noticed that there are different approaches to work on the pupils' zone of proximal development. Some teachers seem to have a good understanding of the concept and they are able to provide specific strategies, while others are not familiar with the concept and have no idea of what it stands for. The common strategies mentioned by the teachers include: breaking the lesson into discrete units, pre-teaching vocabulary, using visual aids, identifying the pupils' current level of understanding, providing support and guidance, simplifying the lesson using realia/pictures, besides the use of the mother tongue (Algerian Dialectal Arabic). Some teachers model the lessons and assign tasks and activities to their pupils.

5.3 OBSERVATION-BASED ANALYSIS

Observation, as a data collection tool provides researchers with insights to observe verbal and non-verbal expressions, identify interlocutors, how they interact with each other, and detect the credibility of the questionnaire responses. As we have observed, teachers employ various strategies to enhance pupils' learning. They integrate prior knowledge by drawing on personal experiences, using analogies, and facilitating reflective discussions. Group work and projects promote collaboration and social skills while making learning more enjoyable. Furthermore, the use of audio-visual aids reinforces understanding and caters to diverse learning styles. Also, the existence of gender equality ensures equal participation and a positive environment. Furthermore, the challenge of managing disruptive behavior in the classroom, as well as the complexities of catering to the needs of pupils with special needs, besides the difficulties faced by teachers in maintaining an effective classroom environment. In fact, each research method has advantages and disadvantages, this entails that the observation has weaknesses too due to subjectivity and bias (Driscoll, 2011). Therefore, a double entry notebook- as Driscoll has referred to- is used to separate between what was observed from what is interpreted to prevent subjectivity (Belaid, 2020). Only the variables that are related to our research objectives in all schools were analysed.

Table 3: The research double-entry observation

<i>Observed Attributes</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Teachers play a crucial role in incorporating pupils' prior knowledge into their teaching practices. All participants (teachers) use a warm up before initiating the course, their ways vary from one teacher to another, sometimes they succeed in warming up their prior knowledge and some other times, pupils face difficulties in interpreting the teachers' lesson objectives	The teacher helps pupils connect new concepts with their prior knowledge through strategies like relating to personal experiences, using analogies and metaphors, and building on prior lessons, facilitating reflective discussions. These approaches enhance understanding and retention of the new material by establishing meaningful connections with what pupils already know.
Pupils in class were required to work in groups, a group of 4-5 members. The organization was easy in classes where the number of students is low whereas, in overclouded classrooms, it was difficult for teachers to control these groups. Their peer groups where random and each group might have 3 active learners altogether while in another slow learners and disruptive attitude learners are gathered in on group. Thus, group work management was somewhat controlled.	Teachers allow their pupils to work in groups and projects to promote their development of social and collaborative skills. They make learning more enjoyable and engaging by encouraging interaction, teamwork, and communication among peers. Pupils benefit from sharing ideas, learning from one another, and actively applying knowledge to real-world scenarios. However, active learners in one group make them finish the task early and initiate disturbing the others, and this was a weakness in management.

Teachers rarely use of Audio-Visual Aids in class when delivering lectures. Though, at this level, ICTs facilitate the transmission of knowledge to learners.	The infrequent use of ICT in class can lead to several outcomes including, reduced engagement, limited understanding and difficulty to address the different learning styles of learners.
Some pupils face difficulties in uttering a phrase, their pronunciation of words is incorrect, the pitch is high, mixture of Arabic and English in their utterances.	Some pupils cannot read a phrase and struggle with pronouncing each word separately. This could be the outcomes of confusion between French, Arabic and English because the three linguistic systems are taught to pupils in their third grade simultaneously.
Some pupils are able to translate words from English to Arabic, their linguistic system of Arabic is active while learning English. The use of the mother tongue in the classroom; Teachers do not rely mainly on English or body language, when failing to transmit knowledge to their pupils, teachers directly use Algerian Dialectal Arabic to clarify words.	Certain pupils in the classroom can translate a limited set of words from English to Arabic and sometimes to French; this suggests that these pupils may have proficiency in these languages; however, their translation abilities may be limited to specific words or phrases. The Linguistic background of Arabic is introduced unintentionally within the process of learning English.
Excessive energy is displayed by some pupils (hyperactivity traits). They are impatient and move all around the rows of the classroom. Their hyperactive character disturbs their peers.	There are hyperactive pupils inside the classroom who have high levels of energy, restlessness, and impulsivity; these pupils have difficulty in sitting, paying attention, and following instructions, which always cause disruption in the learning environment. Even the other pupils notice this disorder, they laugh and enjoy this attitude and some of them attempt to do the same.
Attentiveness and lack of concentration is apparent in class, some students are less attentive than the others.	We have noticed that these pupils make noise during the lesson, but they are very smart and friendly; they are able to interact with the teacher and have the capacity to understand and create words. The negative side about them is their slower pace of understanding.
Pupils communicate with each other using mixed codes, English, Arabic and body language.	Pupils are able to build a simple discussion between them (interviewer, interviewee), and they also interact well with their teacher, especially when learning pronunciation and speaking through challenges, songs, and pictures. But still this production is limited (absence of fluency and accuracy).
Comprehension and Production difficulties are experienced by some pupils. These learners have different learning styles and preferences, this difficulty is written as well as oral.	Some pupils struggle with expressing themselves verbally for example, some pupils cannot detect and interpret a picture /video, or produce in the writing form; these pupils may have difficulties in finding the right words to convey their thoughts and with language development in general.

5.4 ADDRESSING CLASSROOM DISRUPTION

The inability of some teachers to turn disruptive behavior into positive behavior creates considerable difficulties in classroom management. These teachers are overwhelmed to discover the effective ways and strategies to address and manage disruptive behavior, and this can have a negative effect on the learning environment and the pupils' overall academic success. When teachers are unable to handle inappropriate behavior, it can create a cycle of frustration and tension in the classroom. Students who engage in disruptive behavior may continue to do so due to the absence of consequential discipline. This not only disturbs the learning process, but it also has an impact on the well-being and involvement of other students. By blurting out answers, talking excessively, or participating in off-task actions, classroom disruptions typically disrupt the flow of the

lesson. This made it difficult for some teachers to provide a focused and effective learning environment for all students. When it comes to attention and engagement, individuals often face challenges in maintaining sustained focus on tasks. They are easily distracted or lose interest in activities, which ultimately affects their learning outcomes. Consequently, teachers are required to provide additional support to keep them actively involved. Besides these challenges, we should put stress on overcrowded classrooms by which time and classroom management skills became a priority.

5.4.1 BLENDING SCAFFOLDING AND INCLUSIVE LEARNING

Based on our observations, it is evident that most of the teachers are effectively implementing some of the scaffolding techniques to teach English to their pupils. Some strategies align with this approach, including, schema building, group projects, and supplementing teaching with audio-visual aids. Additionally, the teachers provide support to every pupil, encourage them to speak freely, and offer both encouragement and criticism to aid in language development and self-confidence. Furthermore, the classroom setting fosters active participation and collaborative learning. The teacher encourages pupils to support their classmates, regardless of their difficulties in pronunciation or understanding. This collaborative learning strategy creates a welcoming and inclusive environment, where gender discrimination or stereotyping does not occur. It is important to provide an inclusive learning atmosphere for all pupils. The issue lies in the fact that each teacher is specialized in a certain field of expertise, such as translation or civilization, and may not be familiar with the teaching methods introduced in didactics. As a result, they often rely on the themes provided during the training sessions, but this is not always sufficient to cover all the pedagogical techniques required for effective teaching.

In terms of language development, the instructor speaks slowly, models language, and stimulates critical thinking by allowing students to think aloud. This process is supported by tasks, reading texts, and the usage of videos and audio. Frequent assessments for understanding and the use of metacognitive methods help students learn more effectively. Furthermore, we observed that the pupils actively participate in the classroom and learn the language through imitation, repetition and positive reinforcement.

5.4.2 COLLABORATIVE LEARNING ENVIRONMENT

Encouraging collaboration and interaction among learners is essential for building and maintaining a collaborative learning environment that enhances the process of scaffolding. The instructor also generates opportunities for peer learning and assistance. Collaborative activities, such as group discussions, peer feedback, or cooperative projects can facilitate the sharing of ideas, perspectives, and strategies. The teacher acts as a facilitator, guiding and promoting meaningful interactions among pupils. This collaborative approach fosters a supportive and inclusive learning space where pupils can learn from and with one another. In addition to these specific duties, teachers have to be flexible and adaptable in their approach to scaffolding. They need to constantly monitor and evaluate the learners' progress to determine when and how to modify the amount of support. As learners progress, the teacher gradually reduces the use of scaffolding, allowing them to take greater control of their learning. This procedure necessitates professional intervention and an awareness of the developmental phases of learners. Furthermore, the teachers' expertise extends beyond scaffolding techniques; to scaffold effectively, they should have a deep understanding of the subject matter and instructional strategies, as well as knowledge of effective questioning techniques, instructional resources, and appropriate feedback mechanisms.

6. CONCLUSION

In Algeria, teaching psycholinguistic techniques in primary schools can equip students to thrive in a global environment. The education system in Algeria, particularly in primary schools, do not give great importance to the learners' Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD). Eventhough, this focus helps learners to complete tasks with guidance, which in turn contributes to their growth and development. By providing instruction that aligns with the learners' ZPD, teachers can improve their language proficiency, problem-solving skills, social abilities, and creativity. English language teaching (ELT) is an essential part of education in Algeria. Integrating psycholinguistic insights can lead to a better future for young learners. By using these techniques, educators can create an engaging learning environment that helps pupils understand the complexities of the English language more efficiently. Teachers can tailor their teaching methods to suit individual needs by understanding how students learn and process information, without disregarding pupils with special needs. The integration of psycholinguistic techniques into primary education in Algeria has enormous potential to enhance English language teaching and equip students with the skills needed for success in an era of digital proliferation.

References

- Abdelshaheed, M. S. B. (2019). Using Instructional Scaffolding Strategies to Support Oral Productive Language Skills among English Majors at Majmaah University. *Arab World English Journal (AWEJ)*, (10) 2. <https://dx.doi.org/10.24093/awej/vol10no2.8>
- Ameri, A. M. & Seyyedrezaei, S. H. (2016). Scaffolding: An Indispensable Technique in Language Teaching. JIEB, Islamic Azad University, Iran.
- American Speech Language Hearing Association (2010). *Roles and Responsibilities of Speech Language Pathologists in schools*. <https://www.asha.org/policy/>
- Beitchman, H. J., & Brownlie, B. E. (2014). *Language Disorders in Children and Adolescents*. Advances in Psychotherapy Evidence-Based Practice. Hogrefe Publishing.
- Belaid, L. (2020). The Impact of Gender and Social Factors on Pupils' Achievement. Unpublished Doctoral Dissertation. University of Mostaganem, Algeria.
- Bertram. R. (2013). *Language Comprehension: An Interdisciplinary Approach*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Cornell, D. (2023). Zone of Proximal Development Examples. The Helpful Professor. Retrieved on: 08/09/2023, from: <https://helpfulprofessor.com/zone-of-proximal-development-examples/>
- Driscoll, L. D. (2011). Introduction to primary research: Observations, surveys, and interviews. A published chapter in *Writing Spaces: Readings on Writing*, 2, 153-174.
- Gonulal, T. & Loewen, S. (2018). *Scaffolding Technique (1st edition)*. The Tesol Encyclopedia of English Language Teaching. John Wiley & Sons, Inc. DOI: 10.1002/9781118784235.eelt0180
- Heidari, K. (2022). A Psycholinguistic Look at the Role of Field Dependence/ Independence in Receptive/Productive Vocabulary Knowledge: Does it Draw a Line? *Journal of Psycholinguistic Research*, 51: 1393–1408. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10936-022-09905-4>
- Hussein, A. M. (2022). Scaffolding as a Teaching Strategy to Improve Students Translation Performance. *Journal of Language Studies*, 5 (4), 87-105.
- Johnson, A. (2014). *Cognitive Development: Jean Piaget*. This is an excerpt from my book: Education Psychology: Theories of Learning and Human Development. National Science Press: www.nsspress.com
- Field, J. (2004). *Psycholinguistics: Key Concepts*. Routledge: London and New York.
- Levelt, M. J. W. (2001). Spoken word production: A theory of lexical access. Max Planck Institute for Psycholinguistics. *PNAS*, 98 (23). www.pnas.org/cgi/doi/10.1073/pnas.231459498
- Purba, N. (2018). The Role of Psycholinguistics in Language Learning and Teaching. *Tell Journal*, 6 (1). 47-54.
- Reiser, B. J. (2004). Scaffolding Complex Learning: The Mechanisms of Structuring and Problematizing Student Work. *The Journal of the Learning Sciences*, 13 (3). 273–304.
- Rogoff, B. (1990). *Apprenticeship in Thinking: Cognitive Development in Social Context*. Oxford University Press.
- Sazali, A. R. B., Khamarudin, F. B., & Abdul Alahdad, S. N. B. (2022). Maximising The Zone of Proximal Development Benefits in Group Online Learning. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*. 12 (6), 1476 – 1496.
- Sternberg, J. R. (2008). *The Cognitive Psychology*. California Belmont: Wads Worth.
- Traxler, M. J., & Gernsbacher, M. A. (2006). *Handbook of Psycholinguistics (2nd edition)*. Elsevier: Academic Press.
- Traxler, M. J. (2012). *Introduction to Psycholinguistics: Understanding Language Science*. Hoboken, New Jersey: John Wiley and Sons.
- Treiman, R., Clifton, C., J. Meyer, A. S., & Wurm, L. H. (2003). Language comprehension and production. *Comprehensive Handbook of Psychology, Volume 4: Experimental Psychology*. New York: John Wiley & Sons, Inc. 527-548.
- Vygotsky. L. (1978). *Mind and Society*. Cambridge Massachusetts: Harvard University Press.
- Wernicke. C. (1969). *The Symptom-Complex of Aphasia: A Critical Review*. New York: Grune and Stratton.

Author Biography / Biographies

Belaid Louiza is a researcher and a University lecturer at Ibn Khaldoun University, Tiaret, ALGERIA; she holds a Ph.D in Sociolinguistics and Gender Studies. She has participated in many national and international conferences in Algeria, France, Poland, Romania, Turkey, and Qatar. Miss Belaid has many articles published in indexed journals including JIPED, LLT journal, Language and Linguistic Studies and Journal of Social Sciences and Educational Research. Her areas of interest include TEFL, Discourse Analysis, Pragmatics, Language and Society, Urban Dialectology and Gender Studies.